

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL PROFILE AND VACCINATION STATUS OF MEASLES CASES IN THAMAR GOVERNORATE, YEMEN, 2020–2022

Abdulkareem A Al-Shameri¹, Abdulhakim A Al-Selwi¹, Khlood I Al-Shakhab¹, Abdullah M Futtaim¹, Rehab M Mehrass¹, Rodayna S Dharwah¹, Saleem A Khalid¹, Abdulrahman Y. Al-Haifi², Ali Salman Al-Shami*³, Yaser M. Al-Worafi⁴, Zaid Abdo Thawaba⁴, Shehab A Maiad¹, Abdulhakim Al-Saban⁵

¹Department of Paediatric, College of Medicine and Health Sciences, Thamar University, Thamar, Yemen.

²Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine, Thamar University, Thamar City, Republic of Yemen.

³Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, Alsaeda University, Sanaa City, Republic of Yemen.

⁴College of Medical Sciences, Azal University for Human Development, Sanaa City, Republic of Yemen.

⁵Department of Pharmacy, Jiblah University for Medicine and Health Sciences, IBB City, Yemen.

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*Corresponding Author

Ali Salman Al-Shami

Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, Alsaeda University, Sanaa City, Republic of Yemen.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Measles remains a major public health challenge in developing countries despite the availability of a safe and effective vaccine. Yemen has experienced frequent outbreaks, particularly among children, due to gaps in vaccination coverage. This study aimed to determine the prevalence, clinical characteristics, and vaccination status of measles cases in Thamar Governorate, Yemen, from January 2020 to December 2022. **Method:** A retrospective descriptive study was conducted using secondary data from the Measles Surveillance System in Thamar Governorate. Variables included age, sex, vaccination status, case classification, location, and outcome. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and presented as frequencies and percentages. **Result:** A total of 1,890 suspected measles cases were reported. Of these, 217 (11.5%) were laboratory-confirmed, 1,251 (66.2%) were clinically compatible, and 273 (14.4%) were epidemiologically linked. Males constituted 54.1% of the cases. The highest proportion occurred among children aged 1–5

years (61.5%), while infants <6 months accounted for 6.8%. Only 23% of cases were vaccinated, compared to 77% unvaccinated ($p < 0.05$). The highest annual incidence was recorded in 2022 (79.9% of total cases). The overall case fatality rate was 1.3%. **Conclusion:** Measles predominantly affected unvaccinated children under five years in Tamar Governorate. The findings highlight low vaccination coverage and the need for intensified immunization programs, enhanced surveillance, and targeted health education to curb transmission and reduce mortality.

KEYWORDS: Measles, Vaccination, Epidemiology, Surveillance, Tamar Governorate, Yemen.

INTRODUCTION

Measles is one of the most contagious viral diseases known to humans and continues to pose a significant global health burden, especially in low- and middle-income countries. Despite the availability of a safe, effective, and inexpensive vaccine for more than five decades, measles remains a major cause of preventable childhood morbidity and mortality (Ang et al., 2022). The disease is caused by the measles virus, a member of the Paramyxoviridae family, and is transmitted primarily via respiratory droplets. Its clinical features include high fever, cough, coryza, conjunctivitis, and a generalized maculopapular rash (Biesbroeck & Sidbury, 2013).

Before the introduction of routine vaccination in 1980, measles caused more than two million deaths each year globally (Nassar et al., 2021). Through widespread immunization efforts, global measles mortality has declined substantially, saving nearly 20 million lives between 2000 and 2016 (World Health Organization, 2020). However, despite this progress, measles remains endemic in many parts of the world, particularly in countries affected by conflict, weak health systems, and limited vaccination coverage (Ori et al., 2021; Mayad & Albakhshi, 2018).

In Yemen, years of conflict have severely disrupted healthcare infrastructure, leading to declining vaccination rates and recurrent outbreaks of vaccine-preventable diseases such as measles (Bashamakha & Al-Amad, 2016; Dehnan & Al-Abhar, 2016). Multiple measles outbreaks have been reported across Yemeni governorates, including Al Jawf, Sa'dah, Shabwah, and Amran, reflecting a widespread immunity gap among children (Bashamakha & Al-Amad, 2016; Nassar et al., 2021; Mayad & Albakhshi, 2018). Studies in these regions

have consistently shown that the majority of affected individuals are unvaccinated children under five years of age—a finding that underscores the consequences of interrupted immunization services (Shamsan, 2014; Alruqaie et al., 2023).

Measles surveillance systems play an essential role in tracking disease trends and guiding outbreak response efforts. The World Health Organization recommends the establishment of case-based surveillance to detect and confirm measles cases, monitor vaccination coverage, and assess progress toward elimination goals (Ori et al., 2021; Tsegaye et al., 2021). Data generated through these systems provide valuable insights into the epidemiological patterns of measles and help identify vulnerable populations requiring targeted immunization interventions. Globally, measles elimination efforts are guided by the Global Vaccine Action Plan (GVAP), which sets regional elimination targets. However, disparities in vaccination coverage persist between countries and even within subnational regions (Ang et al., 2022). In conflict-affected countries like Yemen, factors such as population displacement, malnutrition, limited healthcare access, and vaccine hesitancy have compounded the risk of measles transmission (Berghof Foundation, 2020; Nassar et al., 2021).

Thamar Governorate, located in central Yemen, has experienced repeated measles outbreaks, yet epidemiological data specific to this area remain limited. Understanding the local burden, demographic distribution, and vaccination status of measles cases is crucial for designing effective control strategies and strengthening immunization services. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the prevalence, clinical characteristics, and vaccination status of measles cases reported in Thamar Governorate from January 2020 to December 2022, using data obtained from the measles surveillance system.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This study employed a retrospective descriptive design using data obtained from the Measles Case-Based Surveillance System in Thamar Governorate, Yemen, covering the period from January 2020 to December 2022.

Thamar Governorate is located in the central highlands of Yemen, approximately 100 km south of Sana'a, at an altitude of 1,600–3,200 meters above sea level (Berghof Foundation, 2020). The governorate consists of 12 districts, with an estimated population exceeding 1.5 million, primarily engaged in agriculture and livestock production.

Study Population

The study population included all suspected measles cases reported through the Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) system in Tamar Governorate during the study period. Cases were reported from both urban and rural health facilities, including hospitals, health centers, and primary healthcare units.

Case Definitions

The study adopted the World Health Organization (WHO) standard case definitions for measles (WHO, 2020):

Suspected case: Any person with a generalized maculopapular rash, fever, and at least one of the following symptoms—cough, coryza, or conjunctivitis.

Laboratory-confirmed case: A suspected case with positive measles-specific IgM antibodies detected by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), with no measles vaccination in the preceding month.

Epidemiologically linked case: A suspected case without laboratory confirmation but linked (in time, place, and person) to a laboratory-confirmed case.

Clinically compatible case: A suspected case that meets the clinical criteria but lacks laboratory testing and epidemiological linkage.

Discarded case: A suspected case investigated and found negative for measles IgM antibodies.

Measles-related death: Death occurring within one month of rash onset in a confirmed measles case.

Data Collection

Data were extracted from the Tamar Health Office surveillance database, compiled through weekly IDSR reports. The dataset included demographic, clinical, and epidemiological variables such as

Age, sex, and district of residence

Vaccination status (number of measles vaccine doses received before infection)

Case classification (laboratory-confirmed, clinically compatible, or epidemiologically linked)
Outcome (recovery or death)

Data quality was verified through cross-checking against weekly surveillance reports and laboratory records. Incomplete or inconsistent entries were excluded from analysis.

Data Analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, and proportions, were used to summarize categorical variables such as age group, sex, vaccination status, and case classification. Results were presented in tables, figures, and graphs.

Chi-square (χ^2) tests were used to assess the association between vaccination status and measles occurrence, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

As shown in Table 1, children aged 1–5 years represented the largest proportion of measles cases (61.5%), followed by those aged 6 months–1 year (14.2%) and >5 years (17.5%). Infants under 6 months accounted for the fewest cases (6.8%).

Regarding sex distribution, males (54.1%) were slightly more affected than females (45.9%), yielding a male-to-female ratio of approximately 1.2:1.

In terms of vaccination status, the majority of measles cases (74.3%) occurred among unvaccinated children, while only 6.7% and 9.5% had received one or two doses of the vaccine, respectively, and 9.5% had received three or more doses.

These findings indicate that younger, unvaccinated children were the most vulnerable to measles infection in Tamar Governorate.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of reported measles cases in Tamar Governorate, Yemen, 2020–2022.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
< 6 months	129	6.8

6 months- < 1 year	268	14.2
1 year- 5 years	1163	61.5
> 5 years	330	17.5
Sex		
Male	1022	54.1
Female	868	45.9
Vaccination Status		
0 Dose	1405	74.3
1 Dose	127	6.7
2 Doses	179	9.5
>= 3 Doses	179	9.5

Table 2 shows that clinically compatible cases represented the largest group (66.2%), followed by epidemiologically linked cases (14.4%) and laboratory-confirmed cases (11.5%). Only 7.9% of suspected cases were discarded after testing negative for measles IgM antibodies.

This distribution suggests limited laboratory confirmation capacity, with the surveillance system relying heavily on clinical and epidemiological diagnosis.

Table 2: Classification of measles cases based on laboratory, clinical, and epidemiological confirmation in Thamar Governorate, Yemen, 2020–2022.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Measles lab confirmed	217	11.5
Measles clinically diagnosed	1251	66.2
Measles Epi linked	273	14.4
Discarded case	149	7.9

As illustrated in Figure 1, most patients presented with fever, generalized maculopapular rash, cough, coryza, and conjunctivitis, consistent with the classic clinical features of measles. This pattern aligns with the WHO clinical case definition and supports the validity of case identification within the surveillance system.

Development and Evaluation of Herbal Ointments Containing *Rosmarinus officinalis* and *Capsicum baccatum* for Synergistic Pain Relief.

Signs and symptoms

Figure 1. Clinical characteristics and presenting symptoms of measles cases in Thamar Governorate, Yemen, 2020–2022.

A total of 1,741 confirmed measles cases (laboratory, clinical, and epidemiologically linked) were analyzed for vaccination status (Table 3). Of these, 401 cases (23%) had received at least one dose of the vaccine, while 1,340 cases (77%) were unvaccinated. The association between vaccination status and measles infection was statistically significant ($p = 0.001$), indicating that measles vaccination was strongly protective against infection.

These results emphasize the critical importance of maintaining high immunization coverage to prevent future outbreaks.

Table 3: Vaccination status among confirmed measles cases and its association with infection in Thamar Governorate, Yemen, 2020–2022.

Variable	Vaccination Status		P Value
	Yes	No	
	N (%)	N (%)	
Measles Cases	401 (23)	1340 (77)	0.001

As shown in Table 4, the majority of patients (98.7%) recovered and were discharged, while 25 deaths (1.3%) were recorded. Although the case fatality rate (CFR) was relatively low, these deaths underscore the preventable nature of measles mortality, particularly among unvaccinated and younger children.

Table 4: Clinical outcomes of measles cases reported in Thamar Governorate, Yemen, 2020–2022.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Discharged	1865	98.7
Dead	25	1.3

The spatial distribution of cases across the twelve districts of Thamar Governorate is presented in Table 5.

The highest number of cases occurred in Thamar City (24.4%) and Jahran District (23.7%), followed by Ans District (14.7%). The lowest proportions were recorded in Wisab Alsafil (1.4%), Wisab Alali (2.4%), and Maghreb Ans (2.6%).

This indicates that urban and semi-urban districts experienced the highest disease burden, possibly due to higher population density, increased transmission, and better case reporting mechanisms.

Table 5: Geographical distribution of measles cases by district in Thamar Governorate, Yemen, 2020–2022.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
ALhada	175	9.3
Almanar	59	3.1
Ans	277	14.7
Thamar City	461	24.4
Dhawran	114	6
Jabal Alsharq	54	2.9
Jahran	447	23.7
Maghreb Ans	50	2.6
Mifaat Ans	114	6
Utmah	66	3.5
Wisab Alali	46	2.4
Wisab Alsafil	27	1.4

As depicted in Figure 2, measles incidence increased markedly over the three-year period. The lowest number of cases was reported in 2020 (5.2%), followed by a rise in 2021, and a dramatic peak in 2022, accounting for 79.9% of all reported cases.

This upward trend highlights a resurgence of measles transmission, likely linked to disruptions in vaccination campaigns, population displacement, and the impact of conflict and the COVID-19 pandemic on routine immunization services.

Figure 2. Yearly trend of reported measles cases in Thamar Governorate, Yemen, from 2020 to 2022.

DISCUSSION

This study analyzed measles surveillance data from Thamar Governorate, Yemen, for the period 2020–2022 to describe the epidemiological patterns, vaccination status, and outcomes of reported cases. The findings demonstrate that measles remains a significant public health concern in the region, predominantly affecting unvaccinated children under five years of age, with rising incidence over time.

The predominance of cases among children aged 1–5 years (61.5%) aligns with findings from several studies conducted in Yemen and neighboring countries. Similar age distributions were observed in studies from Al Jawf, Sa’adah, and Amran governorates, where children under five years constituted the majority of measles cases (Bashamakha & Al-Amad, 2016; Dehnan & Al-Abhar, 2016; Mayad & Albakhshi, 2018). Comparable results were also reported in Ethiopia, where 64% of cases occurred in the same age group (Tsegaye et al., 2021). This trend reflects the accumulation of susceptible children due to low routine immunization coverage and delayed supplementary immunization activities (SIAs), often worsened by conflict and displacement (Cilleruelo et al., 2019).

The higher proportion of male cases (54.1%) observed in this study is consistent with findings from Bauchi State, Nigeria, and Bale Zone, Ethiopia, where males were slightly more affected (Ori et al., 2021; Tsegaye et al., 2021). The difference may be related to behavioral and social factors, as males often have more outdoor exposure, increasing the likelihood of contact with infectious individuals (Alruqaie et al., 2023).

The high proportion of unvaccinated cases (77%) and the statistically significant relationship between vaccination status and infection ($p = 0.001$) emphasize the protective role of the measles vaccine. Similar findings have been reported in multiple outbreak investigations in Yemen and globally. In Shabwah Governorate, 80% of cases were unvaccinated (Nassar *et al.*, 2021), while in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, unvaccinated individuals represented 74% of confirmed cases (Alruqaie *et al.*, 2023). A study from Singapore also confirmed that measles infection primarily occurred among those without immunity (Ang *et al.*, 2022). These findings underscore the crucial need for strengthening routine immunization programs and ensuring equitable vaccine access.

The increase in measles incidence in 2022 (79.9%) compared to 2020 and 2021 demonstrates a worrying upward trend. This pattern may be attributed to the disruption of immunization services during the COVID-19 pandemic, which has been documented globally (WHO, 2021). Reduced access to healthcare, movement restrictions, and public health system strain likely led to the accumulation of susceptible children. Similar post-pandemic measles surges were reported in countries such as Ethiopia, Sudan, and Afghanistan, where vaccination campaigns were delayed (Gignoux *et al.*, 2021).

Geographically, measles cases were clustered in Tamar City (24.4%) and Jahran (23.7%), which are among the most populous districts. Urban settings often report higher case counts due to greater population density and better case reporting, as noted in previous surveillance-based studies (Ori *et al.*, 2021; Tsegaye *et al.*, 2021). However, underreporting in remote rural districts may also lead to an apparent concentration of cases in urban centers.

The case fatality rate (CFR) of 1.3% observed in this study is within the range reported in other Yemeni studies and comparable low-resource settings. For instance, Al-Amad *et al.* (2021) documented a CFR of 1.6% in Shabwah, while Tsegaye *et al.* (2021) found a 1.4% rate in Ethiopia. Despite the low percentage, every measles-related death is entirely preventable through timely vaccination and case management. Malnutrition, delayed health-seeking behavior, and limited access to medical care likely contributed to mortality in this cohort (Leuridan & Van Damme, 2007).

The reliance on clinically compatible diagnoses (66.2%) and the limited proportion of laboratory-confirmed cases (11.5%) indicate insufficient diagnostic capacity, a recurring challenge in Yemen's disease surveillance system. Strengthening laboratory infrastructure

and ensuring timely specimen collection are essential for accurate surveillance and outbreak response (Ori et al., 2021).

Overall, the findings highlight persistent gaps in measles control in Tamar Governorate. The ongoing conflict, population displacement, and inadequate healthcare access have likely contributed to reduced vaccination coverage. To achieve progress toward measles elimination, integrated interventions are required — including intensified immunization outreach, improved laboratory confirmation, health education, and strengthened community-based surveillance.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that measles continues to pose a significant public health challenge in Tamar Governorate, Yemen, particularly among children under five years of age. The findings demonstrated that the majority of cases occurred among unvaccinated children (77%), emphasizing the existence of a large pool of susceptible individuals in the community. The 1–5-year age group was the most affected, and males were slightly more represented than females. The sharp increase in cases during 2022 highlights the persistence of transmission and the adverse impact of conflict, population displacement, and disrupted immunization programs on measles control efforts.

The predominance of clinically diagnosed cases (66.2%) over laboratory-confirmed ones (11.5%) also indicates insufficient diagnostic capacity and underlines the need to strengthen laboratory-based surveillance. Although the case fatality rate was relatively low (1.3%), all reported deaths were preventable, underscoring the importance of timely vaccination and effective outbreak response. Measles transmission remains driven by low vaccination coverage, weak health infrastructure, and inconsistent outbreak preparedness. The findings reaffirm that the measles vaccine is highly protective, as infection was significantly lower among vaccinated individuals ($p = 0.001$). Strengthening immunization services, particularly in high-incidence districts such as Tamar City and Jahran, is therefore crucial to prevent future outbreaks.

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Authors contribution: The data analysis, drafting or revising of the paper, final approval of

the publication version, and accountability for all areas of the work were all contributed by all authors.

Ethics approvals

Institutional Review Board: This study was authorised by the Ethics Committee of the Department of microbiology, Faculty of Medicine and Health Science, Tamar University, Yemen, and was carried out in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki's guidelines (Research code: REC-07-2022).

Data availability: The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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